

Book Review

Susannah O’Sullivan (2018). *Military Intervention in the Middle East and North Africa: The Case of NATO in Libya*. London and New York: Routledge. Hardback. ISBN: 978-1138669758. Price ₹9840.00. 188 pp.

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The Arab spring that sprout and germinate from Tunisia and spread to Egypt, Libya, Syria, Bahrain and Yemen in 2010–2011 was a tumultuous time in West Asia and North Africa that unlocked “domino effect” in the region leading to the fall of Ben Ali in Tunisia, Mubarak in Egypt, Gaddafi in Libya and the long effect on Yemen crisis and Syria that subsequently led to the toppling of Assad dictatorship regime in 2024. The Libya is an interesting case that receives significant attention from various International Politics and International Relations scholars. Susannah O’Sullivan, a renowned scholar with immense knowledge and expertise in the security studies, post colonialism and the border violence, in her famous book *Military Intervention in the Middle East and North Africa: The Case of NATO in Libya* analyse critically the politics of legitimizing the violence against illegitimate “others” in the border to protect the so called legitimate subject lives. This resulted in obscuring the languages of ethics and protection of civilian lives with that of racist violence. The urgency for mobilization of military action in Libya was projected to be driven over the concern to protect the Europe southern borders following Gaddafi’s threats to destabilize the EU established border regime, which had long relegated migratory flows to authoritarian regimes influence in the North Africa.

Susannah O’Sullivan through the book explores the military intervention in Libya through categories of space and time and provides a robust ethico-political critique of the intervention that draws upon postcolonial and poststructural approaches to critical security studies by questioning the underground layers of ways that rationalize the military response as reasonable to the crisis in Libya, mapping and decoding the false binary between the human and the state. The other aspects that the author unveils is that of a thought process of ‘othering’ during the Libyan intervention and the imagination of Libyan’s as different and inferior. This imaginative

geography of ‘superior self’ and ‘inferior other’ underlines the justification of humanitarian intervention.

The book brilliantly discusses the process of a altercation from “Humanitarian Intervention” to “Responsibility to Protect” where in the 1990’s certain trends were observed what was termed as “security-development nexus” that merged developmental with military aims. The case of Bosnia and Rwanda Aid and the unapproved Kosovo intervention. This account of intense failure subsequently led to intense debate and a shifted from a “right to intervention” to a “responsibility to protect” with a notion of responsibility for a sovereign state to protect the population and in case state abdicate this responsibility, then it falls into international community. This reconfiguration of ‘humanitarian intervention’ was ponder upon from an image of weapon of a strong against the weak.

Susannah O’Sullivan critical analysis of the precision and speed that is term as cheap, quick, bloodless and moral. An argument that intentionally tries to obscures the casualties of civilian to legitimize intervention to gather the support within the political elite in UK, US and the France at the initial stages of intervention is another point that the author discusses. The race against time as Gaddafi’s forces were approaching Benghazi and the limited military action to protect and prevent humanitarian disaster that used urgency, was to avoid parliamentary debate and to sway public emotion as war itself is unlikely to be support by the public in the case of UK and US respectively. The distinction between legitimate and illegitimate modes of violence that was employed in the case of Libyan to destroy the military assets with precision was also critique by author as an imperialist mindset and a means to legitimize the violence. Susannah also question the flexibility over certain emotive phrases such as “collateral damage” and “combatants” where civilian casualties often bypass and not counted as “collateral damage” but as legitimate combatants. Another credit to author critique of the NATO intervention is the civilian casualties resulted from NATO airstrikes and the adamant to admitted as technical system failure and the disinterested concern within NATO leaders to investigate this mistake is noteworthy.

Military Intervention in the Middle East and North Africa also discussed the colonial phases that Libyan underwent with special focus to Italian colonial rule. The significance for such invocation of colonial history is that she pointed out the pattern of colonial discrimination that Italian institutionize specially that of racial hierarchy in their detention system, this segregation of whites-non whites was unleashed again during the 2011 civil war. The subsequent drama that expel Italy through allied power and leading up to the creation of Libyan state that was rather the superficial creation of colonial

rivalries and European power struggles and the Libya soil being tested as a ground where military technique of destruction were tried out painted a gloomy picture of Libyan past that is to repeat in 2011.

Susannah O'Sullivan pointed out the "organised hypocrisy" where after a decade of Sanction on Libya in the early 2000's as the embargo lifted in exchange to destroy the stockpiles of WMD and cooperate in the war on terror and that instead of ending a weapon regime the west compete for a shared of weapon market that armed Gaddafi's and in twisted outcome is used to suppresses against the civilian Libyan population during the Arab spring. There is also a strong British government hand in assistance with Gaddafi's regime in systematic tortured. The case of Al-Saadi, Belhaj and Boudchar torture speaks for itself. Paradoxically, this acts of torture were sustained by the same sense of moral certitude that underlines the proclamation that the uprising of 2011 was to lead a path of peace and democracy in Libya. Apart from weapon and counter terrorism the author has also pointed out the west collaboration with Gaddafi's regime in managing and control of migration from the bordering North African states like Libya. This "European Neighbourhood policy" was stated to give a famous quote, "Europe Neighbourbecoming Europe's policeman". Italy a former colonial that colonized Libya provided assistance by funding detention camp, paying repatriation flights and marine interception missions and police cooperation. This migration from African countries were cunningly link with democracy and as a result France become the forefront leader to intervene in Libya in 2011 and to supply arms to rebels to ousted Gaddafi's and bring democracy and stability that will addressed the roots cause of migration. This attitude and intention of France and other EU member were question by the author of its primary motivation which appears to be rather maintenance of strict buffer zones to stem migration in North Africa that is deemed to threatened its sovereignty and thus not humanitarian concern.

The imaginative geographies that underpin the process of "othering" represents the Libyan uprising where the rebels were caught between victim, freedom fighter and enemy, not able to fulfill a role of saviour that was reserved for western forces to intervene reflect the orientalist assumption of Arabs within western narration and its foreign policy. The author had beautifully crafted out this narrative of a clear delineated hierarchical parental relationship in the international system between those who intervene and those who are recipients of intervention. The parental hierarchy also reflect in designating the rebels as juvenile, rag-tag armies, incompetent, militarised and threatening, sometimes even linking with potential Al-Qaeda. The hierarchical imagination of emerging states as children in decolonisation debates with binaries such as mature/immature

and responsibility/irresponsibility becomes the eligibility of practical independence. This subordinate subjectivity is painted as one in transition towards legitimacy and as somewhere that lies in between three topology of savage-victim-saviour of international human rights discourses.

The aftermath of post Gaddafi's regime was predicted to be a playground of tribal chaos and a struggle for power between competing militias and also concern by heightened targets on western consulate. Libya was divided into three government: The UN backed government of National Accord, the Tobruk House of representatives and the general national congress, based in Tripoli.

The book provides an insightful historical trajectory that takes a reader to the colonial cruelty that civilian went through a painful phases to the creation of Libyan state where the anticipation for better projection of future to which many Libyan shed their blood for was met with the same fate during the Gaddafi's regime except that here the boss shifted to local, a son of its soil but the brutality of that colonial leader, to put into Macaulay words, "Libyan's by blood, but colonial by thoughts"[author inputs]. The book gives us a glimpse of what a thought process went through western elite and the motivation behind such initiatives for urgent intervention. This narratives is significant as the book navigated through other ends of perspective that of military perspective and European. However, there are certain loopholes or shortcomingthere were limited emphasizes on Gaddafi's brutality and also the narratives from Libyan ruling elite as well the civilian perspective or their thought process are undocumented. The book also thrown itself more in contextual analysis that of decoding the speeches of western leaders and their perspective and thus the Libyan's academician and intellectual sources are limited or unjustly overlooked.

However, despite several shortcoming it will be handy for beginner who seeks to understand the Libya colonial history and also in its state creation and particularly The trajectory from humanitarian intervention to R2P with details analysis on Arab uprising. Lastly, although the price of the book is undoubtedly pricy the book is worth it. Thus, the book is recommend as a must read not only for academics from security studies, international relations and international politics but also for student that seek to have a glance into West Asia and North African region.